

EMPOWEREDbyNEIA

(Grant Agreement: 101134912)

Ecosystems Mapping and Planning through Open dialogue for Wider cooperation across EU Regions based on the Entrepreneurial Discovery

D.3.2 Public Funding Repository

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Authors	Antonela Marincat, Fahimeh Mousavi, All partners
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1. Introduction

This deliverable, D.3.2 Public Funding Repository, represents the key output of ‘Task 3.2 – Identifying resources to support the implementation of the action plans’ under work package 3 (WP3) of the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project. It provides a comprehensive overview of the primary public funding opportunities available (2024-2025) at European level and within the project partners’ national and regional level.

The core objective of Task 3.2 is to systematically map the existing funding landscape, spanning public funding sources across national, regional, and European levels. The result of this effort is a robust and accessible repository, designed as an actionable agenda of public funding opportunities. This repository serves as an essential tool for innovation stakeholders, fostering strategic connections with funding agencies, industry players, and local investors to drive impactful projects forward.

A distinctive element of this deliverable is its detailed documentation of funding opportunities specific to each partner region. The repository features tailored sections that highlight national, regional, and local funding programmes in Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Estonia, Italy, Poland, and Romania. By focusing on the unique funding landscapes of these regions, the deliverable ensures that stakeholders within diverse ecosystems can access relevant and context-specific information. This targeted approach helps address disparities in funding accessibility and promotes meaningful cross-border collaboration.

1.1 Background on EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project

The European Innovation Policy encompasses a range of initiatives, instruments, and investments addressing diverse challenges, needs, and opportunities. However, regional disparities, territorial inequalities, and limited connectivity between ecosystems highlight the need for stronger synergies and policy coherence to better align sectoral priorities, policies, and key innovation players. To address these issues, the New European Innovation Agenda (NEIA) aims to unify and harmonize policies to accelerate the development and scaling of innovation across Europe.

Aligned with NEIA, the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project, a Horizon Europe-funded initiative under the European Innovation Ecosystems initiative, seeks to empower regional innovation ecosystems by facilitating the emergence of collaborative, community-based activities and co-designing of Joint Action Plan. This project aims to enhance connections within European innovation systems while fostering policy alignment at the broader European level. Additionally, EMPOWEREDbyNEIA strengthens cooperation among quadruple helix stakeholders through an inclusive, gender-sensitive, mutual learning process at national and regional levels. It envisions shared tools and resources to support startups and scale-ups in driving innovation.

The EMPOWEREDbyNEIA consortium comprises a diverse group of venture accelerators, regional innovation and development agencies, and support organizations from seven European countries—Italy, Austria, Poland, Romania, Bulgaria, Croatia, and Estonia. The consortium’s goal is to unite innovation ecosystem members across these regions, enabling them to identify the strengths, weaknesses, challenges, and gaps in each ecosystem. This collaboration aims to foster connections among key innovation actors, paving the way for implementing joint action plans. The project began in January 2024 and is set to conclude in December 2024.

2. Online repository of Funding opportunities

The funding opportunities identified in this deliverable have been published on the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project website, under the dedicated section “**Fundings**” (Link: <https://www.empoweredbyneia.eu/fundings/>).

This online repository provides an accessible and user-friendly platform for stakeholders to explore a wide range of public funding opportunities at European, national, and regional levels. The Fundings section of the website includes:

- **Comprehensive listings:** a well-organized repository categorizing funding opportunities by region, funding type, and sector focus to facilitate easy navigation.
- **Search and filtering tools:** interactive features to help users locate relevant opportunities based on specific criteria such as geographic location, type of funding, or upcoming deadlines.
- **Ongoing updates:** regular maintenance and updates ensure that the repository reflects the latest funding calls, modifications, or new opportunities as they become available.

This publication on the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA website ensures that the funding repository is widely accessible, maximizing its impact by supporting innovation actors in accessing crucial resources.

3. List of Public Fundings

3.1 Available European Grants (2024-2025)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR/project)	Type	Call document/link
1	Support to the activities of the SET Plan Key Action area Renewable fuels and bioenergy	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-13	04/02/2025	600,000	Lump sum CSA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
2	Development of next generation synthetic renewable fuel technologies	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-02	04/02/2025	4 mil	RIA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
3	Resource Efficiency of PV in Production, Use and Disposal	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-07	04/02/2025	3 mil	Lump sum CSA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
4	Minimisation of environmental, and optimisation of socio-economic impacts in the deployment, operation and decommissioning of offshore wind farms	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-08	04/02/2025	5 mil	Lump sum RIA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
5	Innovative, Community-Integrated PV systems	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-06	04/02/2025	5 mil	IA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
6	Demonstrations of innovative floating wind concepts	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-09	04/02/2025	15 mil	IA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
7	PV-integrated electric mobility applications	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-05	04/02/2025	7 mil	IA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
8	Market Uptake Measures of renewable energy systems	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-10	04/02/2025	2 mil	Lump sum CSA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
9	Digital tools for CSP and solar thermal plants	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-01	04/02/2024	3 mil	Lump sum IA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR/project)	Type	Call document/link
10	CULTURAL CHANGE FOR GREEN TRANSITION	ESA	23/08/2024	75,000		Cultural Change for Green Transition (esa.int)
11	Small-scale partnerships in adult education (KA210-ADU) 2024	Erasmus+	01/10/2024	30,000 /60,000	Lump sum	Small-scale partnerships - Erasmus+ (europa.eu)
12	RFCS-2024 Coal and Steel Research Projects	RFCS	24/09/2024	1 - 20 mil		call-fiche_rfcs-2024_en.pdf (europa.eu)
13	Bio-intelligent manufacturing industries (Made in Europe Partnership) (RIA)	HORIZON-CL4-2024-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-01	24/09/2024	5 mil	Lump sum RIA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
14	Biodegradable polymers for sustainable packaging materials (IA)	HORIZON-CL4-2024-RESILIENCE-01-35	24/09/2024	8 mil	IA	Horizon Europe Calls 2024 - Destination 2. Increased autonomy in key strategic value chains for resilient industry (two-stage) - European Commission (europa.eu)
15	Specialised Education Programmes in Key Capacity Areas	DIGITAL-2024-ADVANCED-DIGITAL-07-KEYCAPACITY	21/11/2024	9 mil	Lump sum	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
16	Interregional Innovation Investments Strand 1	I3-2024-INV1	05/12/2024	10 mil	I3-AG	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
17	Interregional Innovation Investments Strand 2a	I3-2024-INV2a	05/12/2024	10 mil	I3-AG	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
18	Capacity Building Strand 2b	I3-2023-CAP2b	14/11/2024	1,5 mil	I3-AG	Capacity Building Strand 2b (I3-2023-CAP2b) - European Commission (europa.eu)
19	Rethinking urban spaces towards climate neutrality	HORIZON-MISS-2024-CIT-01-01	11/02/2025	15 mil	IA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
20	Zero-pollution cities	HORIZON-MISS-2024-CIT-01-02	11/02/2025	5 mil	RIA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
21	Integrated peri-urban areas in the transition towards climate neutrality	HORIZON-MISS-2024-CIT-01-04	11/02/2025	9 mil	IA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR/project)	Type	Call document/link
22	Mobility Management Plans and Behavioural Change	HORIZON-MISS-2024-CIT-01-03	11/02/2025	5 mil	CSA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
23	MARITIME DECARBONISATION	ESA	28/02/2025	-	Grant	Maritime Decarbonisation (esa.int)
24	Systemic and cross-sectoral solutions for climate resilience, tailored to the local needs of regions and local authorities	HORIZON-MISS-2024-CLIMA-01-09	18/09/2024	9 mil	IA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
25	Bringing together the national level with the engaged regional and local levels (multi-level governance)	HORIZON-MISS-2024-CLIMA-01-02	18/09/2024	4 mil	CSA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
26	Bringing available and actionable solutions for climate adaptation to the knowledge of the regions and local authorities	HORIZON-MISS-2024-CLIMA-01-01	18/09/2024	2 mil	CSA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
27	Improve design for transformative approaches and build local capacity for implementation of available solutions focused on climate adaptation	HORIZON-MISS-2024-CLIMA-01-05	18/09/2024	4 mil	RIA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
28	Improved transport infrastructure performance – Innovative digital tools and solutions to monitor and improve the management and operation of transport infrastructure	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D6-01-08	05/09/2024	5 mil	IA	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-cl5-2024-d6-01-08
29	Policies and governance shaping the future transport and mobility systems	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D6-01-09	05/09/2024	3 mil	RIA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
30	Strategic Integrated Projects - Climate Action	LIFE-2024-STRAT-CLIMA-SIP-two-stage	05/09/2024	30 mil	Grant	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
31	Supporting national, regional and local authorities across Europe to prepare for the transition towards climate neutrality within cities	HORIZON-MISS-2021-CIT-01-01	05/09/2024	2 mil	CSA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR/project)	Type	Call document/link
32	Climate Governance and Information	LIFE-2024-SAP-CLIMA-GOV	17/09/2024	5 mil	Grant	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
33	Climate Change Mitigation	LIFE-2024-SAP-CLIMA-CCM	17/09/2024	28,5 mil	Grant	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
34	BUILD UP Skills – Upskilling and reskilling interventions for building decarbonisation	LIFE-2024-CET-BUILDSKILLS	19/09/2024	6,5 mil	Grant	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
35	Clean energy transition plans and strategies in municipalities and regions	LIFE-2024-CET-LOCAL	19/09/2024	7 mil	Grant	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
36	One-Stop-Shops - Integrated services for clean energy transition in buildings and businesses	LIFE-2024-CET-OSS	19/09/2024	7 mil	Grant	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
37	Supporting the clean energy transition of European businesses	LIFE-2024-CET-BUSINESS	19/09/2024	5,2 mil	Grant	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
38	Crowding in private finance	LIFE-2024-CET-PRIVAFIN	19/09/2024	5,2 mil	Grant	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
39	LIFE Clean Energy Transition – Standard Action Project	LIFE-2024-CET-SAP	19/09/2024	4 mil	Grant	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
40	ERA Talents	HORIZON-WIDERA-2024-TALENTS-03-01	26/09/2024	3 mil	CSA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
41	Hop on Facility	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-06-01	26/09/2024	0,6 mil	RIA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR/project)	Type	Call document/link
42	Electricity, Gas, Smart Grids, Hydrogen and CO ₂ networks - Studies	CEF-E-2024-PCI-PMI-STUDIES	22/10/2024		Grant	EU Funding & Tenders Portal EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
43	Robotics and other automated solutions for construction, renovation and maintenance in a sustainable built environment (Built4People Partnership)	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D4-02-02	04/02/2025	4 mil	RIA	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
44	Enterprise Europe Network	SMP-COSME-2024-EEN-01	04/02/2024	25,6 / call	EEN	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
45	CLIMATE RISK ASSESSMENTS FOR EVERY EUROPEAN REGION	Climaxx	15/10/2024	0,3 mil	Lump Sum	climaax OnePass (getonepass.eu)
46	Open call for project platforms	Interreg Baltic	21/10/2024	1,5 mil	Grant	Gateway for applicants - Interreg Baltic Sea Region (interreg-baltic.eu)
47	Development Innovation Ventures (DIV)	USAID	1/11/2024	15 mil \$	Grant	Search Results Detail Grants.gov
48	Specialised Education Programmes in Key Capacity Areas	DIGITAL-2024-ADVANCED-DIGITAL-07-KEYCAPACITY	21/11/2024	9 mil	Lump Sum	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
49	Call for peripheral and lagging areas	Interreg CE	12/10/2024	0,75 mil	Grant	Call for peripheral and lagging areas • Interreg.eu
50	Visegrad Fund Strategic Grants	Visegrad Fund	01/02/2025	0,5 mil	Grant	Strategic Grants International Visegrad Fund - Visegrad Fund
51	Visegrad Grants	Visegrad Fund	01/02/2024	0,2 mil	Grant	Visegrad Grants International Visegrad Fund - Visegrad Fund
52	Teaming for Excellence	HORIZON-WIDERA-2025-ACCESS-01-01-two-stage	10/05/2025	15 mil	Grant	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
53	Eureka Open call for Network projects applications	Eureka - Network	31/12/2025	0.1 mil	Grant	Open call for Network projects applications - Eureka (eurekanetwork.org)
54	Global Innovation Fund	GIF	Ongoing	15 mil \$	Grant	Global Innovation Fund Apply for Funding

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR/project)	Type	Call document/link
55	Global Innovation Fund	GIF	Ongoing	15 mil \$	Grant	Global Innovation Fund Applying to the Innovating for Climate...
56	Austrian Development Agency Business Partnerships	ADABP	Ongoing	0,5 mil	Grant	Business Partnerships - Austrian Development Agency (entwicklung.at)
57	City Climate Finance Gap Fund	CCFGF	Ongoing	0,2 mil	Grant	Turning resilient low-carbon ideas into strategies and finance-ready projects CityGapFund
58	EU4ENVIRONMENT		Ongoing		Grant	https://www.eu4environment.org/
59	European Environment Agency	EEA	Ongoing		Grant	https://www.eea.europa.eu/about-us/tenders/open-calls-for-tenders
60	Creative Innovation Labs	CREA-CROSS-2025-INNOVLAB	24/04/2025	5 mil euro /call	Grant	call-fiche_crea-cross-2025-innovlab_en.pdf
61	Joint Cluster Initiatives (EUROCLUSTERS) for Europe's recovery	SMP-COSME-2024-CLUSTER	05/02/2025	42 mil	Grant	Joint Cluster Initiatives (EUROCLUSTERS) for Europe's recovery (SMP-COSME-2024-CLUSTER) - European Commission
62	Maritime regional cooperation fostering Smart Specialisation and Innovation in the Sustainable Blue Economy (Topic 1)	EMFAF-PJG EMFAF	18/02/2025	5,7 mil	Grant	EU Funding & Tenders Portal
63	Teaming for Excellence (HORIZON-WIDERA-2025-ACCESS-01)	HORIZON-CSA HORIZON	10/04/2025	270 mil total	Action Grant	EU Funding & Tenders Portal
64	SKILLS AND TALENT DEVELOPMENT	CREA	24/04/2025	7,5 mil	Grant	Creative Europe Programme CALL Skills and talent development Digital Skills and Jobs Platform
65	Demonstrating feasibility and environmental benefits of regenerative ocean farming and boosting algae innovation (Topic 2)	EMFAF-PJG EMFAF	18/02/2025	1,9 mil	Action Grant	EU Funding & Tenders Portal
66	Support to the activities of the SET Plan Key Action area Renewable fuels and bioenergy	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-13	04/02/2025	0,6 mil	Grant	Support to the activities of the SET Plan Key Action area Renewable fuels and bioenergy – HORIZON Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02-13) - European Commission
67	Transport calls for proposals	CEF	21/01/2025	160 mil	Grant	2024 CEF Transport calls for proposals - European Commission

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR/project)	Type	Call document/link
68	Strategic Nature Projects (SNaP)	LIFE-2024-STRAT-NAT-SNaP-two-stage	06/03/2025	n/a	Grant	Strategic Nature Projects (SNaP) - European Commission
69	Strategic Integrated Projects – SIP Environment	LIFE-2024-STRAT-ENV-SIP-two-stage	18/04/2025	n/a	Grant	Strategic Integrated Projects – SIP Environment - European Commission

3.2 Available Cascade funding calls (2024-2025)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR)	Call document/link
1	EIT Community Co-Crete NEB: Local communities and public authorities building sustainable, beautiful and inclusive public space – 2025	EIT-NEB	10/10/2024	n/a	The Co-create NEB call for proposals to build sustainable and inclusive public spaces is now open! EIT (europa.eu)
2	EIT Climate-KIC Call for Expression of Interest: ClimAccelerator Organisers (Europe)	EIT Climate-KIC	14/09/2024	n/a	EIT Climate-KIC Call for Expression of Interest: ClimAccelerator Organisers (Europe) EIT (europa.eu)
3	EIT Regional Innovation Scheme Urban Mobility Specialists (RISUMS) Open Call 2025	EIT Mobility	30/09/2024	n/a	https://eit.europa.eu/our-activities/opportunities/eit-regional-innovation-scheme-urban-mobility-specialists-risums-open
4	Connect New European Bauhaus Open Call 2025	EIT Connect	26/09/2024		Apply for Connect New European Bauhaus Open Call 2025 EIT (europa.eu)
5	Open Innovation Factory 2024	EIT Digital	21/10/2024	400.000/call	
6	Call for financial support to start-ups: Accelerate	EIT Manufacturing	16/12/2024	n/a	Permanently Open Call for financial support to start-ups: Accelerate EIT (europa.eu)
7	Q2Scale Programme: empowering start-ups to scale globally through real-world validation	EIT Global Outreach	30/11/2024	n/a	Q2Scale Programme: empowering start-ups to scale globally through real-world validation EIT (europa.eu)
8	Call for proposals for new Higher Education Institutions to join Master and Doctoral Schools	EIT Manufacturing	05/12/2024	50.000/call	Call for proposals for new Higher Education Institutions to join Master and Doctoral Schools EIT (europa.eu)
9	Individual or Collaborative Projects of tourism SMEs	ST3ER	30/09/2024	25.000/project	Calls for Projects – ST3ER
10	xBUILD-EU 2nd call for proposals	xBuilld-EU	02/10/2024	20.000 - 50.000 project	Launch of xBUILD-EU second call - Tèxtils.CAT (textils.cat)
11	3rd REINFORCING Open Call (Incubators Call) on Missions	REINFORCING	25/09/2024	60.000 / project	Reinforcing
12	OPEN CALL FOR PROPOSALS for Social Economy SMEs in Energy Intensive Industries	SEE BRIDGE	01/10/2024	4.000 - 8.000 / project	Open Call - SEE BRIDGE (infoproject.eu)
13	Gemstone open calls	GEMSTONE	31/12/2024	1,500 - 2,200 / project	Gemstone – Support manufacturing SMEs in their green transition initiatives (projectgemstone.eu)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR)	Call document/link
14	Call for Financial Support to Innovation Individual Services	ELBE	31/08/2024	10,000 / project	ELBE EUROCLUSTER Call for Financial Support to Innovation Individual Services Atlantic Action Plan Atlantic Strategy (europa.eu)
15	Call for Pilots	DS4SSCC	31/08/2024	1,5 mil / project	European Data Space for Smart Communities (ds4sscc.eu)
16	NGI Zero Core 8th Open Call	NGI	01/10/2024	50,000 / project	NGI Open Calls Next Generation Internet
17	EIT Manufacturing TRANSFORM Call 2024 (multiple cut off)	EIT - Manufacturing	29/10/2024	20,000 / project	EIT Manufacturing Submission Manager - TRANSFORM Call 2024 (submittable.com)
18	RESIST: Internationalisation Open Call (multiple cut-off)	RESIST	20/12/2024	60,000 / project	RESIST Internationalisation activities Open Call European Cluster Collaboration Platform
19	European Partnership on Innovative SMEs / Innowwide CALL 3 (InnovativeSMEs)	Innowwide CALL 3	15/10/2024	86,000 / project	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
20	Rivers Revived - Open Call for Associated Regions	DALIA	16/10/2024	100,000 / project	EU Funding & Tenders Portal (europa.eu)
21	Third CommuniCity Open Call 2024-2025	ComuniCity	31/10/2024	50,000 / project	CommuniCity (communicity-project.eu)
22	EIT Food Impact Funding Framework	EIT Food	14/11/2024	750,000 /project	EIT Food Impact Funding Framework - EIT Food
23	EIT RawMaterials Booster Call	EIT Raw Materials	16/09/2022	500,000 / project	EIT Raw Material - Booster Call
24	ScienceUs Citizen Science call – Upscaling and interconnecting ongoing citizen science projects relevant to the EU mission “Adaptation to climate change”.	ECO-TANDEM	06/01/2025	40,000 / project	ScienceUs Citizen Science call -Upscaling and interconnecting ongoing citizen science projects relevant to the EU mission “Adaptation to climate change” - Πύλη Ενημέρωσης Χρηματοδοτικών Προγραμμάτων - ΓΔ Ανάπτυξης

3.3 Available Private-Public investments (2024-2025)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR)	Call document/link
1	Common Fund for Commodities (CFC) 25TH CALL FOR PROPOSALS	CFC	01/10/2024	1,5 mil	Call for Proposals Common Fund for Commodities (common-fund.org)
2	Call for Applications: Llama 3.1 Impact Grants	Llama 3.1	22/11/2024	0,5 mil	Call for Applications: Llama 3.1 Impact Grants (meta.com)

3.4 Available Funding in Austria (2024-2025)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR)	Call document/link
1	ecoplus Regionalförderung	Supports sustainable regional projects, especially those in Green Tech and Clean Tech sectors. The program supports initiatives under the "Green Transformation & Bioeconomy" platform, aiming to foster sustainability and the circular economy.	ongoing submissions.	not stated on website.	Regionalförderung (ecoplus.at)
2	COIN (Cooperation & Innovation)	Is designed to support applied research and development, focusing on fostering cooperation between companies and research institutions, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). This program encourages innovation and technology transfer, promoting the development of innovative products, services, and processes.	yearly submissions, last deadline was on March 27, 2024.	For the 2024 calls, a total of €4 million is available for funding innovative projects.	COIN (bmaw.gv.at)
3	aws Energie & Klima	Aimed at supporting start-ups and small to medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in implementing energy and environmental projects, with a focus on energy management systems and transitioning innovative energy and environmental technologies to industrial-scale production.	Applications can be submitted anytime until 30 June 2025.	Funding up to €200,000 for projects, with up to 50% for energy management systems and 25% for the industrialization of start-ups' technologies. Project duration can last between 1 to 2 years.	aws Energie & Klima - Austria Wirtschaftsservice
4	aws Building(s) Tomorrow	This initiative supports radical and disruptive innovations in the building sector, aiming to drive significant advancements in sustainability and the circular economy. It focuses on both technological and social innovations in building construction, operation, and demolition to reduce resource consumption and lower greenhouse gas emissions.	The next call is expected to open on February 22, 2025.	The program offers a non-repayable grant of up to €100,000, covering up to 80% of eligible project costs.	aws Building(s) Tomorrow - Austria Wirtschaftsservice

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR)	Call document/link
5	TWIN Transition – Sustainable and Digital Transformation of Businesses	This program supports companies that are pioneers in their industries by helping them transition towards sustainable and digitalized production processes and products.	Applications are open continuously from November 8, 2023.	Up to €200 million is available for funding. Individual project budgets start at a minimum of €4 million, with funding tailored according to project scope and EU aid rules.	TWIN Transition - Austria Wirtschaftsservice (aws.at)
6	aws Green Frontrunner - Wachstumsinvestition	This program supports Austrian companies aiming to become market or technological leaders with a focus on sustainability. It encourages projects that align with climate and environmental goals as part of the European Green Deal.	Applications are open on a rolling basis.	Up to €1 million in funding is available for each project, covering investment and development costs. Projects can also be combined with an aws ERP loan for additional financial support.	Green Frontrunner - Austria Wirtschaftsservice (aws.at)
7	aws Innovationsschutz mit Selbstbehalt	Protecting and fostering innovation within Austrian companies in the Green Tech sector.	Applications can be submitted at any time.	Funding covers up to €200,000, with eligible project costs ranging from €20,000 to €150,000. The grant covers 50-80% of the costs depending on the specific module.	IP Management, Intellectual Property, Schutzrechte, Green IP, GreenIP, Green Tech, grüne Technologien - Austria Wirtschaftsservice (aws.at)
8	Klima- und Energiefonds - Stadt der Zukunft	Klima- und Energiefonds	typically annual, last deadline was Q4 2023, new call to be	varies per project (previous calls allocated up to 50 million per project)	

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR)	Call document/link
			expected Q4 2024		
9	Produktion der Zukunft (Production of the Future)	FTI-Initiative (Research and Technology Initiative) initiated by the Austrian Ministry for Climate Action	Regular calls; specific deadlines vary per call (check the ongoing opportunities)	Total funding depends on the call, typically in millions (for example, €2.5 million for a recent call)	Produktion der Zukunft – die FTI-Initiative FFG
10	Öko-Scheck	FFG, supported by the Austrian Ministry for Climate Action	05 March 2024 - 08 April 2024 (expeted again in 2025)	Maximum €12,000 per project, covering 80% of project costs, with total eligible costs capped at €15,000. The program focuses on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and non-profits aiming to adopt sustainable business practices	Öko-Scheck FFG
11	Internationale Energieagentur (IEA) – Forschungsk Kooperation	IEA Technology Collaboration Programmes (TCPs), with a focus on Austria's participation in global energy research and development initiatives	Typically runs between May and July each year.	In previous years, the total budget was around €2.7–2.8 million, with funding provided for Austrian participation in IEA projects, including research services and development activities.	Forschungsk Kooperation Internationale Energieagentur FFG
12	Energy Transition 2050	FFG - Focuses on societal and economic transitions towards a carbon-neutral and sustainable future,	The 5th call was open from 7	Up to €432,000 in total funding was	Energy Transition 2050 FFG

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR)	Call document/link
		emphasizing social innovations and transition processes that facilitate the energy transition and mitigate climate change impacts.	November 2022 to 22 February 2023. New deadlines should be checked based on current calls.	available for the 5th call, with funding distributed across different research and development services.	
13	FFG - AI for Green (part of AI Ökosysteme 2024)	AI for Green aims to support cooperative R&D projects that utilize or develop AI technologies to contribute to Austria's climate goals. The program focuses on reducing resource and energy consumption, avoiding greenhouse gas emissions, and preserving ecosystems.	Open for submissions from May 15, 2024, to October 8, 2024.	The total budget is approximately €9 million, with individual project funding based on project needs and specific instruments. Each R&D service can receive up to €100,000 (excluding VAT).	AI Ökosysteme 2024: AI for Tech, AI for Green und AIM AT FFG
14	FTI-Initiative für die Transformation der Industrie	This program is part of Austria's Klima- und Transformationsoffensive and aims to support the transformation of Austria's industrial sector by funding innovative technological solutions that reduce greenhouse gas emissions and enhance sustainability in production processes.	The call will be open from June 19, 2024, to October 31, 2024.	The total budget for the 2024 call is €25 million, with the potential to increase by another €25 million from the 2025 budget.	FTI-Initiative für die Transformation der Industrie 2024 FFG
15	FFG Basisprogramm	The program is open to all companies, including startups and SMEs, and covers research and development (R&D) projects. It supports the development of products, processes, or services that have high market potential. The program is technology-neutral and open to all sectors, including Green Tech and Clean Tech.	Applications can be submitted at any time on a rolling basis.	Typically, the program funds 50% of project costs, with startups receiving up to 70%. Project volumes can go up to €3 million, and financing is often a mix of grants	Basisprogramm - Förderung, Bedingungen FFG

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR)	Call document/link
				and low-interest loans.	
16	FFG Impact Innovation	This program supports projects that aim to solve a problem for which no satisfactory solution currently exists. It promotes the use of innovation methods to generate new ideas and develop impactful solutions in any industry or field.	Applications can be submitted on an ongoing basis, with no specific deadline.	The program provides funding of up to 50% of eligible project costs, with a maximum grant of €75,000. The total project budget can be up to €150,000.	Impact Innovation – Funding, Guidelines FFG
17	Vienna Planet Fund	With the Vienna Planet Fund, we support companies from Austria and abroad as well as start-ups from all sectors in the development of climate-friendly products, technologies or services. Come to Vienna with your national or international company and let our team advise you free of charge.	application on a rolling basis, twice a year funding decision 31. August 30. November	max 250.000 per project and max 45% of total project costs, project duratation max 2 years	Förderung Vienna Planet Fund - Wirtschaftsagentur

3.5 Available Funding in Bulgaria (2024-2025)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (BGN)	Call document/link
1	Protection of industrial property rights in enterprises	Program Competitiveness and Innovations in Enterprises 2021-2027	Expected in Nov. 24/ deadline: Feb.2025	23.99 million	To be published on https://eumis2020.government.bg/bg/s/Default/Index
2	Introduction of Industry 4.0 technologies in enterprises	Program Competitiveness and Innovations in Enterprises 2021-2028	Expected in Nov. 24/ deadline: Feb.2025	101.7 million	To be published on https://eumis2020.government.bg/bg/s/Default/Index
3	SME's new production models in the Northern regions of Bulgaria	Program Competitiveness and Innovations in Enterprises 2021-2028	Expected in Nov. 25/ deadline: Jan.2026	90 million	https://www.eufunds.bg/sites/default/files/uploads/opic/docs/2024-10/Proekt_IGRP_PKIP_2025.pdf
4	SME's green technologies on the territory of industrial park	Program Competitiveness and Innovations in Enterprises 2021-2028	Expected in March 25/ deadline: June 2025	162.324 million	https://www.eufunds.bg/sites/default/files/uploads/opic/docs/2024-10/Proekt_IGRP_PKIP_2025.pdf
5	Sustainable development of Centres of Excellence and Centres of Competence, including specific infrastructures or clusters thereof by the National Research Infrastructure Roadmap	Program Research, Innovation and Digitization for Smart Transformation 2021-2027	01.10.2024	336 million	https://eumis2020.government.bg/bg/s/8d3ebf57-ff75-4ad5-afa1-5747f558ee98/Procedure/Info/f013a482-35c3-4afb-950c-cf094e5e3025
6	Small Innovative and grants for small and Medium enterprise (SMEs)	Program Research, Innovation and Digitization for Smart Transformation 2021-2027	Expected in July 24/ deadline: Dec.2025	25 million	To be published on https://eumis2020.government.bg/bg/s/Default/Index
7	Green and Digital Partnerships for Smart Transformation	Program Research, Innovation and Digitization for Smart Transformation 2021-2027	Expected in July 24/ deadline: Dec.2025	60.77 million	To be published on https://eumis2020.government.bg/bg/s/Default/Index

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (BGN)	Call document/link
8	Programmes about Collaboration for Innovation and Knowledge and Technology Transfer	Program Research, Innovation and Digitization for Smart Transformation 2021-2027	Expected in June 24/ deadline: May.2025	172 million	To be published on https://eumis2020.government.bg/bg/s/Default/Index
9	Support for Development for Existing Innovation Clusters	Program Research, Innovation and Digitization for Smart Transformation 2021-2027	Expected in July 24/ deadline: Oct.2025	48 854 million	To be published on https://eumis2020.government.bg/bg/s/Default/Index

3.6 Available Funding in Croatia (2024-2025)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (BGN)	Call document/link
National - Croatia					
1	Proof of Concept	National recovery and resilience plan 2021.-2026.	Deadline 2.12.2024. (recurring)	Grant €6.4M total	https://fondovieu.gov.hr/pozivi/115
2	Support for Technology transfer offices	National recovery and resilience plan 2021.-2026.	Deadline 31.12.2024. (recurring)	Grant €0.5M total	https://fondovieu.gov.hr/pozivi/71
3	Support for companies in meeting applicable standards, conformity assessments, and certification of products/services/processes	Competitiveness and cohesion program 2021-2027.	Call expected 14.10.2024. / Deadline 31.12.2026.	Grant €20M total	To be published https://eufondovi.gov.hr/
4	Innovation for newly established SME's	Competitiveness and cohesion program 2021-2027.	Call expected 30.10.2024. / Deadline TBD	Grant €14.6M total	To be published https://eufondovi.gov.hr/
5	Digitalization of services in local and regional government	Competitiveness and cohesion program 2021-2027.	Call expected 31.10.2024. / Deadline 31.12.2026.	Grant €11.7M total	To be published https://eufondovi.gov.hr/
6	Support for SMEs related to internationalization and market expansion (including participation in international fairs, business meetings, economic delegations, matchmaking or b2b events at home and abroad, and informative events on the topic of internationalization).	Competitiveness and cohesion program 2021-2027.	Call expected 31.10.2024. / Deadline 31.12.2026.	Grant €29.8M total	To be published https://eufondovi.gov.hr/
7	Support for SMEs to join value chains to establish long-term supplier relationships through process and/or business innovations with other companies in a strategic segment	Competitiveness and cohesion program 2021-2027.	Call expected 4.11.2024. / Deadline 4.2.2025.	Grant €7.5M total	To be published https://eufondovi.gov.hr/
8	Strengthening the competencies of students and young researchers for smart specialization and industrial transition	Competitiveness and cohesion program 2021-2027.	Call expected 4.11.2024. / Deadline 31.12.2026.	Grant €10.6M total	To be published https://eufondovi.gov.hr/

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (BGN)	Call document/link
9	Targeted scientific research	Competitiveness and cohesion program 2021-2027.	Call expected 2.12.2024. / Deadline 3.3.2025.	Grant €34.8M total	To be published https://eufondovi.gov.hr/
10	Support for newly established SME's in knowledge-intensive industries (TRL 2-5)	Competitiveness and cohesion program 2021-2027.	Call expected 2.12.2024. / Deadline 3.3.2025.	Grant €13.9M total	To be published https://eufondovi.gov.hr/
11	Innovation vouchers for SMEs	Competitiveness and cohesion program 2021-2027.	Deadline 31.12.2026	Grant €4.9M total	https://eufondovi.gov.hr/poziv/?id=76f3e722-89ee-4a1c-972b-9a89560858d0
Regional - Croatia					
12	Support for the digitalization of SME business operations in the process of industrial transition of Croatian regions	Integrated territorial program 2021.-2027.	Call expected 30.12.2024. / Deadline 31.3.2025.	Grant €30M total	To be published https://eufondovi.gov.hr/
13	Horizontal integrated transformation project to support the strengthening of regional ecosystems for industrial transition	Integrated territorial program 2021.-2027.	Call expected 16.9.2024. / Deadline 16.10.2024.	Grant €5M total	To be published https://eufondovi.gov.hr/ https://hamagbicro.hr/
14	Just transition	Integrated territorial program 2021.-2027.	Call expected 15.11.2024. / Deadline 15.03.2025.	Grant €9.5 total	https://eufondovi.gov.hr/indikativni-godisnji-plan-objave-poziva/

3.7 Available Funding in Estonia (2024-2025)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (BGN)	Call document/link
1	Support for knowledge-intensive activities of Ida-Viru entrepreneurs	Enterprise Estonia	15.10.2024 at 16:00	15 mil total	https://eas.ee/toetused/vke-arenguprogramm/
2	Support of the company's research and development employee	Enterprise Estonia	16.09.2024 at 4:00 p.m.	3 mil total	https://eas.ee/toetused/teadus-ja-arendustootaja-toetus/
3	Support of the infrastructure of an enterprise providing research and development services	Enterprise Estonia	Application for support is ongoing	10 mil total	https://eas.ee/toetused/ta-taristu-toetus/

3.8 Available Funding in Italy (2024-2025)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR)	Call document/link
National - Italy					
1	Industrial Development R&D Circular Economy	MIMIT	Active	Grant From €500,000 up to €2,000,000	https://www.incentivi.gov.it/it/catalogo/economia-circolare
2	Transition Plan 5.0 - Support for the digital and energy transformation of companies in Italy	MIMIT	Active	Tax credit €12,7M total	https://www.mimit.gov.it/it/incentivi/piano-transizione-5-0
3	Patents+, Trademarks+ and Designs+ for SMEs	MIMIT	Not yet	Grant €32M total Up to €60,000.00 per company	https://www.mimit.gov.it/it/incentivi/brevetti-marchi-e-disegni
4	IPCEI Hydrogen 3 (H2 Infra)	MIMIT - IPCEI (EU)	Active	Grant €994M total	https://www.mimit.gov.it/it/incentivi/ipcei-idrogeno-3-h2-infra
5	IPCEI Hydrogen 4 (H2 Move)	MIMIT - IPCEI (EU)	Active	Grant €22M total	https://www.mimit.gov.it/it/incentivi/ipcei-idrogeno-4-h2-move
6	Voucher 3I - Investing in Startup innovation	MIMIT	Not yet	Voucher €9M total Up to €8,000 (+VAT) per company	https://uibm.mise.gov.it/index.php/it/voucher-3i-investire-in-innovazione
7	Industrial Development “Net Zero and Renewables and Batteries” (PNRR)	MIMIT - Invitalia - Development Contracts	Active	Grant/Loan €1,74M total	https://www.invitalia.it/cosa-facciamo/sosteniamo-grandi-investimenti/contratto-di-sviluppo/sportello-net-zero-pnrr
8	New Semiconductor	MIMIT - Invitalia - Development Contracts	Active	Grant €3.292,000,000 total	https://www.invitalia.it/cosa-facciamo/sosteniamo-grandi-investimenti/contratto-di-sviluppo/sportello-semiconduttori
9	Automotive Sector	MIMIT - Invitalia - Development Contracts	Active	Grant € 525M total From €20M € 525M total	https://www.invitalia.it/cosa-facciamo/sosteniamo-grandi-investimenti/contratto-di-sviluppo/sportello-automotive

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR)	Call document/link
10	Sustainable Investments 4.0 – PN RIC 2021-2027 Incentives for SMEs in Southern Italy	Invitalia - FESR 2021-2027	29/09/2023	Grant €400M total Up to 75% of eligible costs	https://www.invitalia.it/cosa-facciamo/rafforziamo-le-impresenuovi-investimenti-sostenibili-40
11	Smart&Start Italy	Invitalia - PN RIC 2021-2027	Active	Grant/Loan From €0,1M up to €1,5M	https://www.invitalia.it/cosa-facciamo/creiamo-nuove-aziende/smartstart-italia
12	Women's Business Fund	Invitalia - PNRR	Active	Grant/Loan €10M total	https://www.invitalia.it/cosa-facciamo/creiamo-nuove-aziende/fondo-impresa-femminile/cosa-finanzia
13	Circular Economy	Invitalia - MISE	Active	Grant/Loan €219,8M total	https://www.invitalia.it/cosa-facciamo/rafforziamo-le-impreseeconomia-circolare
14	Green New Deal - Research, development and innovation projects for ecological and circular transition	MIMIT - CDP Venture Capital Sgrl	Active	Loan €600M total From €3M up to €40M	https://www.mimit.gov.it/it/incentivi/green-new-deal
15	Found Green Transition	CDP Venture Capital Sgrl - NextGeneration EU	Active	VC Direct Funds and Funds of Funds €250M total	https://www.cdpventurecapital.it/cdp-venture-capital/it/fondo_green_transition.page
16	Found Digital Transition	CDP Venture Capital Sgrl - NextGeneration EU	Active	VC Direct Funds and Funds of Funds €300M total	https://www.cdpventurecapital.it/cdp-venture-capital/it/fondo_digital_transition.page
17	Fund Accelerator - Business Validation	CDP Venture Capital Sgrl	Active	VC Direct Funds and Funds of Funds €203M total	https://www.cdpventurecapital.it/cdp-venture-capital/it/fondo_acceleratori.page
18	ZERO Accelerator - Verical Cleantech	CDP Venture Capital Sgrl - Elis		€80K for each startup	https://www.zeroacceleratorcleantech.com
19	Fund Boost Innovation - corporate venture co-creation	CDP Venture Capital Sgrl	Active	VC €75M total	https://www.cdpventurecapital.it/cdp-venture-capital/it/fondo_boost.page
20	Startup Relaunch Fund	CDP Venture Capital Sgrl	Active	VC €200M total	https://www.cdpventurecapital.it/cdp-venture-capital/it/fondo_rilancio.page
21	Programme and Fund for PoCs	ENEA	Not Active		https://www.media.enea.it/en/press-releases-and-news/years-archive/year-2023/research-enea-invests-5-5-

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR)	Call document/link
					million-euros-to-develop-new-technologies-with-private-enterprises.html
22	Knowledge Exchange Program (KEP)	ENEA	Active		https://www.kep.enea.it
Regional – Lazio Region					
22	Chamber of Commerce of Rome. CER 2024 Call. Non-repayable financing in the form of vouchers to support the creation of new Renewable Energy Communities.	CCIAA di Roma. Bando CER 2024.	15/11/2024	Voucher	https://www.contributieuropa.com/bandi/cciaa-di-roma-bando-cer-2024-finanziamento-a-fondo-perduto-sotto-forma-di-voucher-in-sostegno-alla-costituzione-di-nuove-comunita-energetiche-rinnovabili/ https://www.rm.camcom.it/archivio43_bandi-altri-bandi_0_242.html
23	Circular economy	Lazio Innova - ERDF (EU)	Open call from late October 2024	Grant €30M total	https://www.lazioinnova.it/app/uploads/2024/07/Scheda-Bando-Circular-Economy-def.pdf
24	Energy efficiency and renewable for businesses	Lazio Innova - ERDF (EU)	Not yet	Grant €40M total	https://www.lazioinnova.it/bandi/efficienza-energetica-e-rinnovabili-per-le-imprese/
25	New Fund for Small Credit – Energy	Lazio Innova - ERDF (EU)	Active	Loan (0% interest) €13,4M total	https://www.lazioinnova.it/bandi/nuovo-fondo-per-il-piccolo-credito-energia/
26	Energy Efficiency and Renewable for Business	Lazio Innova - ERDF (EU)	Not yet	Grant €40M total	https://www.lazioeuropa.it/bandi/efficienza-energetica-e-rinnovabili-per-le-imprese/
27	LAZIO Venture 2 (LV2)	Lazio Innova - ERDF (EU)	Not yet	Found of Founds €44,6M total	https://www.lazioinnova.it/news/presentata-la-nuova-strategia-per-il-venture-capital/
28	VENTURE TECH Lazio (VTL)	Lazio Innova - ERDF (EU)	Not yet	Found of Founds €12,04M total	https://www.lazioinnova.it/news/presentata-la-nuova-strategia-per-il-venture-capital/
29	TT VENTURE Lazio (TTVL)	Lazio Innova - ERDF (EU)	Not yet	Found €3,31 M total	https://www.lazioinnova.it/news/presentata-la-nuova-strategia-per-il-venture-capital/
30	INNOVA Venture 2 (IV2)	Lazio Innova - ERDF (EU)	Not yet	Found €5,25 M total	https://www.lazioinnova.it/news/presentata-la-nuova-strategia-per-il-venture-capital/
Private Funds					
31	almpact	almpact	Active	VC	https://aimpact.org/
32	Ener2Crowd	Ener2Crowd	Active	Equity and Lending Croudfunding	www.ener2crowd.com/it/

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR)	Call document/link
33	Circular Economy and Green Transition	a2a	Active	CVC From €500k up to €3M	https://innovation.gruppoa2a.it/it/metodo/corporate-venture-capital
34	Eden Venture - Pre seed investment	IAG	Active	CV From €0,2M up to €1,5M	https://www.italianangels.net/startup/
35	Open Innovability®	Enel Group	Active	crowdsourcing	https://openinnovability.enel.com/
36	Eni Next	Eni	Active	CVC	https://www.eni.com/eninext/en-US/home.html
37	Climate Tech Fund	360 Capital	Active	VC	https://www.360cap.vc/focus#ecological
38	Fund I - Technology Transfer	Eureka! Venture Sgr	Active	VC	https://www.eurekaventure.it/
39	MITO Tech Ventures (Climate Tech)	MiTo Technology	Active	VC	https://www.cleantechforeurope.com/news/the-italian-cleantech-space-has-great-potential-mito-technology-joins-cleantech-for-europes-investor-coalition-2
40	Nerva I	Neva Sgr	Active	VC	https://www.nevasgr.com/content/neva/it.html
41	Nerva I Italy	Neva Sgr	Active	VC	https://www.nevasgr.com/content/neva/it.html
42	Innovation Ecosystem Development Fund	Neva Sgr	Active	VC	https://www.nevasgr.com/content/neva/it.html
43	<i>Agnostic fund</i>	Nova Capital	Active	VC	https://www.novacapital.eu/it.html
44	<i>Agnostic fund</i>	P101	Active	VC	https://p101.it/
45	<i>Agnostic fund</i>	2100 Ventures	Active	VC	https://www.2100.vc/

3.9 Available Funding in Poland (2024-2025)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR)	Call document/link
1	Common Fund for Commodities (CFC) 25TH CALL FOR PROPOSALS	CFC	01/10/2024	1,5 mil	https://www.common-fund.org/call-for-proposals/
2	Fundusze Europejskie dla Nowoczesnej Gospodarki / European Funds for a Modern Economy (FENG)		2021-2027	10 billion	https://www.nowoczesnagospodarka.gov.pl/
3	Fundusze Europejskie na Infrastrukturę, Klimat, Środowiska (FENIX) / European Funds for Infrastructure, Climate, Environment (FENX)				https://www.feniks.gov.pl/
4	Optymalizacja gospodarki surowcami i odpadami w przemyśle (Optimization of resources and waste management in the industry sector)		31.12.2024	40 million PLN	https://www.feniks.gov.pl/strony/dowiedz-sie-wiecej-o-programie/nabory/harmonogram-naborow-wnioskow/

3.10 Available Funding in Romania (2024-2025)

#	Topic name	Programme	Deadline	Budget (EUR)	Call document/link
1	North - West Region SMEs digitalization	PRNV/2023/121/1	Active	16,7 mil total	https://regionordvest.ro/prioritati-de-finantare/prioritati-de-finantare-1/
2	Investments in production for Northwest Region SMEs	PRNV/2023/121/2	Active	20 mil total	https://regionordvest.ro/prioritati-de-finantare/prioritati-de-finantare-1/
3	Raising of competitiveness of SMEs in the Nort-West Region	PRNV/2023/121/3	Active	46,7 mil total	https://regionordvest.ro/prioritati-de-finantare/prioritati-de-finantare-1/
4	Intelligent specialization parks	PRNV/2023/121/4	Active	49,5 mil total	https://regionordvest.ro/prioritati-de-finantare/prioritati-de-finantare-1/
5	Development by SMEs of initial investments into intelligent specialization parks	PRNV/2023/121/5	Active	14 mil total	https://regionordvest.ro/prioritati-de-finantare/prioritati-de-finantare-1/
6	Business incubators	PRNV/2023/132.B.1/1	Active	5,8 mil total	https://regionordvest.ro/prioritati-de-finantare/prioritati-de-finantare-1/